

A new methodology to assess the performance and uncertainty of source apportionment models in intercomparison exercises

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HIGHLIGHTS

- The strength of the described methodology derives from its comprehensive approach.
- The preliminary tests check whether source/factors belong to a given source category.
- The performance tests assess the bias with respect to pre-defined quality standards.
- A synthetic testing dataset is provided including the procedure for its creation.
- The new SID indicator is suitable to compare source or factor profiles.

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ABSTRACT

A new methodology to assess source apportionment model performance in intercomparison exercises, encompassing the preparation of real-world and synthetic datasets and the evaluation of the source apportionment results reported by participants, is described. The evaluation consists of three types of tests: complementary tests, preliminary tests, and performance tests. The complementary tests provide summary information about the source apportionment results as a whole. The preliminary tests check whether source/factors belong to a given source category. Three types of indicators: Pearson correlation (Pearson), standardized identity distance (SID), and weighted difference (WD) are used to test factor/source chemical profiles, while factor/source time series and contribution-to-species values are tested only using the Pearson. The performance tests, based on international standards for proficiency testing, are targeted at evaluating whether the reported biases in the quantification of the factor/source contribution estimates (SCEs) and uncertainties are consistent with previously established quality standards in a fitness-for-purpose approach. Moreover, the consistency of the SCE time series is evaluated using a variant of the RMSE normalised by the reference standard uncertainty.

The described methodology facilitates a thorough evaluation of the source apportionment output. The new indicator to compare source or factor profiles presented in this study (SID) is more robust and provides additional information compared to the existing ones.

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1. Introduction

Reliable estimations of the amounts pollution sources contribute to measured ambient air pollution concentrations are essential for the design of effective air quality policies. Receptor

models (RMs) are among the most common source apportionment (SA) techniques (Viana et al., 2008a; Belis et al., 2013). The basic principle of RMs is that atmospheric pollutant sources can be identified and apportioned by solving a mass conservation equation (e.g. Friedlander, 1973; Schauer et al., 1996).

If the number and nature of the sources are known, the problem can be solved using an effective variance least squares approach known as chemical mass balance (CMB) model. The RMs not using a

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priori information about the sources are known as multivariate factor analytical (MFA) methods. More detailed descriptions of RMs are available elsewhere (e.g. Hopke, 2010; Watson et al., 2008; Belis et al., 2014). The main output of a source apportionment model is the mass concentration of a given pollutant deriving from every source category and are known as source contribution estimates (SCE).

Different approaches have been used to compare the performance of different models on the same dataset: comparison of models' SCE mean and standard deviation for each source type (e.g. Favez et al., 2010; Hopke et al., 2006; Larsen et al., 2008), comparison between observed and modelled particulate matter (PM) mass concentrations (e.g. Stevens and Pace, 1984; Viana et al., 2008b), correlation analysis (e.g. Favez et al., 2010; Hopke et al., 2006; Sandradewi et al., 2008) and regression analysis between SCE provided by different models (e.g. Rizzo and Scheff, 2007; Sandradewi et al., 2008). In some studies, the comparison was between different approaches applied by a single research group, which makes the tested alternatives consistent but not really independent. In other studies, more similar to proficiency tests, results obtained by different groups on the same dataset were compared. The simplest test was the comparison of the SCEs and their range of variability while more complex statistical analyses were used to achieve a more complete comparison. Nevertheless, the employed metrics were in general focused on specific aspects of the source apportionment output (SCEs or profiles) and the boundary between comparable and non-comparable results was not clear. Moreover, the evaluations from different studies were not fully comparable among each other due to the lack of common standards to assess the source apportionment model output.

The methodology presented in this study was developed within the framework of the European Commission - Joint Research Centre initiative on source apportionment (<http://source-apportionment.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>) and the Forum for Air quality Modelling in Europe (FAIRMODE). It has been tested on PM datasets and was used to evaluate the performance of RMs in two intercomparison exercises (IEs) whose results are presented in the companion paper by Belis et al. (2015, submitted).

2. Overview of the methodology

The methodology aims at: a) gathering information about the comparability between different models or tools including the influence of the practitioners and b) assessing the uncertainties in the source apportionment model outputs with particular reference to the SCEs.

An intercomparison exercise (IE) for RMs consists of comparing the results of source apportionment analyses performed by independent practitioners on the same dataset using different models. The performance evaluation is accomplished by comparing the differences between the SCEs reported by participants and a reference value with an acceptability criterion.

To perform an IE for RMs, a test dataset containing concentrations of chemical species for a number of samples is required. In IEs with real-world datasets, the source apportionment results reported by participants (in the following, reported source apportionment or reported results) is validated against the reference SCEs derived from the average of participants' results (only those that pass the preliminary tests, see Sections 4.2.1 and 4.3). Also the ability of practitioners to deal with true measurement's noise and inconsistencies can be tested with this kind of dataset. On the other hand, synthetic datasets provide reference SCEs that are internally consistent from a mathematical point of view ("true" values are known). Nevertheless, the data noise introduced "*a posteriori*," is not fully comparable with the uncertainties and variability in real-

world measured data.

Considering that CMB results are based on measured source chemical profiles while the MFA tools report estimated factor chemical profiles, in the following, the general term "factor/source" is used to denote those reported in the participants' source apportionment results. Moreover, "reference source" refers to a source or factor used as benchmark for the evaluation of the reported results. In this study, factor/source chemical profiles are expressed as the relative abundance of each species j to the mass attributed to the source k .

The assessment of the reported results is made for each factor/source separately, and the results are then aggregated by participant, source category, or model.

The evaluation methodology encompasses three types of tests (Fig. 1).

Complementary tests provide ancillary information about the overall consistency of the reported results. They do not assess the accuracy of the factor/source contributions' identification and quantification.

The preliminary tests assess whether the factors/sources reported by participants belong to a given source category (identification). They compare factor/sources on the basis of their chemical profile (fingerprints), the time trends of their contributions (time series), and the percentage contribution of each species to each factor/source (contribution-to-species). Contribution-to-species receives different names in the most commonly used packages: % of species total matrix (EPA PMF v3), factor fingerprint (EPA PMF v5), explained variation (PMF 2), and contribution by species (CMB 8.2). In the preliminary tests, the comparison between source apportionment results was accomplished using the Pearson and a new indicator: the standardized identity distance (SID). In addition, the weighted difference (WD, Karagulian and Belis, 2012) was used to assess the uncertainty of the source profiles. These indicators are described in detail in Section 4.2. The performance tests are based on the methodology proposed in ISO 13528 (2005) and Thompson et al. (2006). These tests aim at assessing whether the contributions of source/factors attributed to a given source category are consistent with previously established quality criteria expressed as standard uncertainty. Moreover, the SCE time series were evaluated using the root mean square error (RMSE) normalised by the standard deviation/uncertainty of the reference value (Jolliffe et al., 2009; Thunis et al., 2012) as described in Sections 4.1.1 and 4.3.2.

3. Input datasets

3.1. Real-world dataset

Typical datasets for source apportionment consist of two dimensional arrays with columns representing species concentrations and rows corresponding to samples. In addition, uncertainty for every entry in the first matrix is required in the most common RMs: positive matrix factorization (PMF) and chemical mass balance (CMB).

The number of samples and the time resolution of the dataset should be suitable to represent the variability of the emissions and meteorological conditions in the area (Brown and Hafner, 2005; Belis et al., 2014). The list of chemical species should include major components (elemental carbon (EC), organic carbon (OC) and ions) and tracers like inorganic trace elements and organic compounds (molecular markers). Datasets where chemical analyses were accomplished using methodologies with known analytical quality performance are required.

In receptor model analysis, previous knowledge of the study area is required for the model execution and interpretation of results. In order to make sure that all participants have access to the

Evaluation Methodology

Complementary tests: provide ancillary information about the model output performance

Mass apportionment
Number of factor/sources

Preliminary tests: test if source/factors belong to a given source category

Chemical profiles —————> Pearson, Pearson (log-transformed), SID, WD

Time-trends —————> Pearson

Contribution-to-species (%) —> Pearson

= % of species total matrix (EPA PMF v3) = explained variation (PMF 2) = contribution by species (CMB 8.2) = factor fingerprint (EPA PMF v5)

Performance tests Evaluate if source/factor SCEs fall within an established quality objective

z-scores —> test SCE bias coherence with the quality objective (σ_p)

zeta-scores —> test SCE reported uncertainty coherence with the one of the reference

RMSE_u —> test the bias, amplitude and phase of the SCE time trends

Fig. 1. Schematic description of the evaluation methodology. SID: standardized identity distance, WD: weighted difference, RMSE_u: uncertainty normalised root mean square error.

same information, it is advisable to distribute local source profiles, emission inventories, and meteorological data for the period under examination.

The first round of the European IE was carried out using a real-world dataset. The final dataset was built up by merging two independent datasets obtained in the Saint Louis supersite between 2001 and 2003 consisting of inorganic and organic species, respectively. The real-world dataset consisted of 178 samples (24-h) with 42 species (Lee et al., 2006; Jaekels et al., 2007).

The dataset distributed to participants already contained the uncertainties for each entry. Nevertheless, to allow participants wishing to check or make their own estimation of uncertainties (facultative), detection limits (DLs) and analytical uncertainties were provided. A summary of the emission inventories of the monitoring area was distributed with the intercomparison package.

The site name and location was not revealed to participants. They were asked to perform all the necessary steps to prepare the dataset for the analysis and to report the methodological choices taken during data pre-treatment, analysis and interpretation using a questionnaire (more details in the companion paper by Belis et al. (2015, submitted)).

3.2. Synthetic dataset

The second round of the European intercomparison was accomplished using a synthetic dataset. In order to generate a dataset matching as much as possible real-world patterns, the CAMx modelling system including the particulate source apportionment technology (PSAT) was employed. PSAT uses reactive tracers to apportion primary PM, secondary PM, and gaseous precursors to secondary PM among different source categories and source regions (Yarwood et al., 2004). The modelling analysis was conducted for the calendar year 2005 over a computational domain covering the whole Po Valley based on a grid resolution of 5×5 km. The source apportionment analysis was performed for the whole

domain and data extracted for one receptor site corresponding to the Milan urban area.

Typical PSAT runs use the PM species: sulphate (SO₄), particulate nitrate (NO₃), ammonium (NH₄), elemental carbon (EC), primary organic aerosol (POA), crustal fine, other fine, crustal coarse, and other coarse. In order to obtain source profiles with trace elements and organic markers comparable to those used in receptor models, the PSAT was set to track 28 emission categories (PSAT groups) defined on the base of those available from the California Air Resources Board (CARB, 2011) database, the SPECIATE 4.3 database (<http://www.epa.gov/ttnchie1/software/speciate/>) and local source profiles (Colombi et al., 2010) (Table 1).

To remove the collinearity observed in some PSAT groups, sources were pooled in eight chemically distinct source categories: Ammonium Nitrate, Ammonium Sulphate, Sea/Road Salt, Biomass Burning, Vehicle Exhaust, Road Dust, Mineral Dust, and Industry. The final dataset containing daily average concentrations of 38 chemical species was generated by combining the contributions of the PSAT pooled sources (source categories) and the chemical profiles of the sources reported by Larsen et al. (2012) in a study conducted in the same area (Table 2).

The relative uncertainty of chemical species in the above mentioned study (reference real-world dataset, RRWD) was used to introduce noise in the synthetic dataset in a realistic manner according to:

$$C_{pert,ij} = C_{ij} + (C_{ij} \times u_{rel,j}) \quad (1)$$

where C_{ij} and $C_{pert,ij}$ are, respectively, the original and perturbed concentrations of species j in sample i and u_{rel} is a normally distributed random variable centred on zero with a standard deviation equal to the species (j) average relative standard uncertainty (i.e. standard uncertainty scaled by the mass of the species). Thus, the species concentrations were perturbed without altering their dataset average values.

Table 1
List of the speciation profiles used to split the PM_{2.5} emission (Mg/y) of each PSAT group. When a combination of profiles was used the relative weight of each profile is shown. If no otherwise specified, source: CARB, 2011.* Source: Speciate 4.3. ** Source: Colombi et al., 2010.

PSAT group	Description of the group	Fuel	name of the profile	%	name of the profile	%	PM _{2.5} [Mg/y]	
1	01ele	0101 – Power Plants	mix	coal/coke combustion	40	gaseous material combustion	60	33.5
2	01ele_bio	0101 – Power Plants	biomass	wood waste combustion	100		0	
3	01ele_oth	0101 – Power Plants	other	coal/coke combustion	40	gaseous material combustion	60	137.6
4	01ene	01 – Energy production in industry (without 0101)	mix	stat. i.c. engine-diesel	50	gaseous material combustion	50	
5	01ene_bio	01 – Energy production in industry (without 0101)	biomass	wood waste combustion	100		0	136.2
6	01ene_oth	01 – Energy production in industry (without 0101)	other	stat. i.c. engine-diesel	50	gaseous material combustion	50	242.2
7	02ris	02 – Domestic and commercial heating	other	residential-natural gas	100		0	3060.7
8	02bio	02 – Domestic and commercial heating	biomass	biomass burning**	100		0	15803.9
9	03cin	03 – Industrial combustion	other	gaseous material combustion	100		0	3371.7
10	03cin_bio	03 – Industrial combustion	biomass	wood waste combustion	100		0	220.3
11	07aut	0701 – Road transport – cars	mix	gasoline vehicles-catalyst	40	diesel vehicle exhaust	60	2100.9
12	07aut_gas	0701 – Road transport – cars	gasoline	on-road gasoline exhaust – composite*	100		0	241.1
13	07aut_die	0701 – Road transport – cars	diesel	lddv exhaust – composite*	100		0	3474.2
14	07aut_gpl	0701 – Road transport – cars	LPG nat. gas	stat. i.c.engine-gas	100		0	25.5
15	07aut_usu	0701 – Road transport – cars (tyre and brake wear)		tyre dust – composite*	100		0	1723.4
16	07tra	07 – Road transport (without 0701)	mix	gasoline vehicles-catalyst	40	diesel vehicle exhaust	60	3062.8
17	07tra_gas	07 – Road transport (without 0701)	gasoline	on-road gasoline exhaust – composite*	100		0	711.3
18	07tra_die	07 – Road transport (without 0701)	diesel	HDDV exhaust – composite*	80	LDDV exhaust – composite*	20	6713.3
19	07tra_usu	07 – Road transport (without 0701; tyre and brake wear)	LPG nat. gas	tyre dust – composite*	100		0	1388.2
20	07eva	07 – evaporation		#n/d	100		0	0.0
21	08off	08 – Off road	mix	diesel vehicle exhaust	100		0	2775.5
22	08off_gas	08 – Off road	gasoline	gasoline vehicles-no catalyst	100		0	48.1
23	08off_die	08 – Off road	diesel	diesel vehicle exhaust	100		0	4405.9
24	09rif	09 – Waste treatment		waste burning	100		0	586.6
25	10agr	10 – Agriculture		feed and grain operations	60	agric. burning - field crops	40	2089.5
26	11nat	11 – Natural emissions (without Sea Salt and BVOC)		grass/woodland fires	100		0	1493.3
27	Bio_ss	Sea Salt and Biogenic VOC		sea salt	100		0	33032.6
28	Other	Other		epa avg: industrial manufac.	100		0	15217.0
29	Dust	Dust from traffic resuspension (simplified model)		dust resuspension**	100			n.a.

Table 2

Source categories (PSAT pooled sources) of the synthetic dataset indicating the origin of the source profiles and the time trends.

Source category	Source profile (Larsen et al., 2012)	PSAT group (time trend)
Ammonium nitrate	AMNITR	1, 3, 4, 6, 7, 9, 12, 13, 14, 17, 18, 21, 22, 23, 25
Ammonium sulphate	AMSULF	1, 3, 4, 6, 7, 9, 25
Sea/road salt	SALT	27
Biomass burning	NM81055	2, 5, 8, 10
Vehicle exhaust	REVEHI	11,12, 13, 16, 17, 18, 21, 23
Road dust	RESOILCA	29
Mineral dust	REBITUM	15, 19
Industry	CEMENT	1, 3, 4, 6

An input data uncertainty was generated independently for every species using the slope of the linear regression equation between concentration and uncertainty in the RRWD (see Supplementary Material S1) according to:

$$u_{ij} = \begin{cases} b_j \times C_{pert,ij} & \text{if } C_{pert,ij} \geq C_{min} \\ C_{min} \times 4 & \text{if } C_{pert,ij} < C_{min} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where u_{ij} is the uncertainty of species j in sample i and b_j is a normally distributed random variable generated using the regression slope and its standard deviation.

For C_{ij} below the minimum observed value for that species in the RRWD (C_{min}), the uncertainty was set to four times the minimum value.

The final dataset contained 364 samples (24-h) with 38

chemical species (see Supplementary Material S2).

4. Evaluation of the source apportionment results

4.1. Complementary tests

4.1.1. Apportioned mass

In order to test the apportioned mass of the reported results, the sum of the mass of all the factor/sources was compared with the reference value attributed to the total PM mass. For *real-world datasets*, the reference was the gravimetric mass concentrations while for synthetic datasets, it was the sum of the mass concentrations of the reference sources. The indicator used for this test was the RMSD* (Jolliff et al., 2009):

$$RMSD^* = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_1^n (m_n - r_n)^2} = \sqrt{B^{*2} + RMSD^{*2}} \quad (3)$$

where m and r denote the modelled and reference values, $RMSD^*$ the root mean square difference, B^* the bias and $RMSD^{*2}$ the unbiased $RMSD$ (more details in [Supplementary Material S3](#)). The asterisk indicates values normalised by the standard deviation of the reference in the whole study time window.

The $RMSD^*$ provides information about the agreement in amplitude and phase between the temporal patterns of the reported results and the reference values, which are often examined using the standard deviation and the Pearson, respectively. It follows from Equation (3) that the $RMSD^*$ summarizes: the bias, the correlation and the ratio of the standard deviations between the reported results and the reference ([Jolliff et al., 2009](#)).

The acceptability criterion for $RMSD^*$ was set to 1 because it represents the condition where the model random error (the stochastic component of error as opposed to the systematic error) is equivalent to the variance of the observations/reference. Points with $RMSD^* < 1$ are also indicating a positive correlation between modelled and observed/reference values ([Jolliff et al., 2009](#)).

As mentioned in Section 2, the factor/sources in every reported output are evaluated separately. The factor/sources that passed the test in the two intercomparisons ranged between 70% and 90% (more details in [Belis et al. \(2015, submitted\)](#)).

4.1.2. Number of factor/sources

RMs apportion the pollutants into sets of sources with high collinearity in their fingerprints and time trends, so called “source categories.” The way in which source categories are defined influences the number of them that can be identified. Splitting a source category into subgroups that contain parts of the same sources is an indicator of poor performance. Alternatively, powerful RM tools may split source categories into more homogenous and distinct subcategories because they are able to better discriminate/resolve collinear sources than others. For that reason, analysing the number of sources without further investigation of the sources features does not lead to a conclusive assessment of a source apportionment result. Only when the definition of source categories is comparable across reported profiles, the ability to find the “true” number of sources is an indicator of the overall performance of the reported result. In synthetic datasets, the number of sources is known and, therefore, the difference between the reported number of sources and the reference can be used as an indicator of the reported source apportionment performance. In real-world datasets, the number of sources to be used as reference must be derived from available studies conducted by practitioners with recognised expertise on the same dataset. Another option is to compare the reported results among each other and consider as most probable the source number with the highest frequency. Although no acceptability threshold is proposed, it is clear that the larger the difference from the reference number of sources, the lower the quality of the reported source apportionment. In the second round of the intercomparison, half of the reported results matched the “true” number of sources (more details in [Belis et al. \(2015, submitted\)](#)).

4.2. Preliminary tests

4.2.1. Indicators of similarity between factor/sources

The Pearson product–moment correlation coefficient (Pearson) is used to compare factor/sources attributed to a source category among each other (ff tests) or with the reference source (fr tests) on

the basis of their: a) chemical profile (fingerprint), b) time series or c) contribution-to-species.

In ff tests, the Pearson coefficients are calculated for all possible pairs of factor/source profiles within each source category and the median is used for the test. The same approach is applied to compare a factor/source with a reference source (fr tests). In this case, there is only one Pearson coefficient per tested factor/source. To establish whether a factor/source profile is comparable to the other factor/source profiles in the same category or to the reference, the most commonly used criterion ranges between $r \geq 0.6$ and $r \geq 0.8$ ([Norris et al., 2008](#); [Paatero et al., 2013](#)). In this study, the lower threshold is used ($r \geq 0.6$).

Pearson is known to be sensitive to the phase in the trend of two variables, but it tells little about the differences in amplitude. Moreover, when the species in a profile show differences in their concentrations of many orders of magnitude, the Pearson may be influenced by one or a few species with high leverage ([Fig. 3](#)). This dependence on large values could produce high Pearson values even for quite dissimilar profiles, and thereby, distort the analysis, especially if the particular species is not a marker for the source category under examination. In order to reduce the excessive influence of species in the high range of concentrations (outliers), Pearson is also calculated using log-transformed profiles according to:

$$x_{kj,log} = \frac{-1}{\ln x_{kj}} \quad (4)$$

where $x_{kj,log}$ is the log transformed value of the relative contribution of species j in source profile k (x_{kj}). A sizeable difference between the Pearson obtained with raw data and log-transformed data (Pearson-log) may indicate that one or few species are highly influential. A limitation of logarithmic transformation is that cannot handle zero values in the profiles.

The identity distance (ID) approach was developed with the aim of addressing the problem of influential species in the Pearson when comparing source profiles.

The ID is defined as the absolute difference between the relative concentrations of species j in two factor/source profiles a and b that were attributed by participants to the same source category in different reported results according to:

$$ID_{j,ab} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} |x_{ja} - y_{jb}| \quad (5)$$

where x_{ja} and y_{jb} denote the relative concentrations of the species in the source profiles a and b , respectively. If the concentration of species j in the profile a is represented on one axis and the concentration of the same species in profile b on the other axis, the identity distance can be geometrically interpreted as the distance of the point (x_{ja}, y_{jb}) to the one-to-one line (identity line) ([Fig. 2a](#)). $ID_{j,ab}$ can be calculated for every common species in profiles a and b ([Fig. 2b](#)). Sources with identical chemical composition are expected to result in scatterplots with all points lying on the identity line. The acceptability thresholds determine the maximum accepted distance (MAD). Geometrically, MAD is the distance between the acceptability threshold and the identity line that passes by point (x_{ja}, y_{jb}) ([Fig. 2a](#)). The MAD expressed in relative units with respect to the source category k ($MAD_{rel,k}$) to be used in IEs is calculated according to:

$$MAD_{rel,k} = \sqrt{MAD_{sou}^2 + MAD_{ana}^2 + MAD_{sec}^2} \quad (6)$$

where MAD_{sou} is the contribution of the source profile uncertainty,

Fig. 2. Geometric representation of the identity distance (ID) as an indicator of similarity between two factor/source profiles. Left pane: $ID_{j,ab}$ between factor/sources a and b for species j with acceptability thresholds (dotted lines); the dot represents point (x_{ja}, y_{jb}) . Right pane: comparison of two hypothetical factor/sources with 10 common species.

MAD_{ana} is the average analytical uncertainty of the input dataset and MAD_{sec} is an additional uncertainty attributed to the secondary sources to account for the assumptions made in the calculation of their SCEs and the difficulty to estimate their uncertainty from the analytical data. On the basis of the experience gained in the two intercomparisons, a value of 0.94 is suggested for MAD_{sec} .

The average of the ID to MAD ratios for all the common species in a pair of profiles, called standardised identity distance (SID), can be used to test the comparability of such profiles (Equation (7)).

$$SID_{ab} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{ID_{ab}}{MAD_{ab}} \quad (7)$$

where n corresponds to the number of species included in both source profiles a and b.

SIDs higher than unity identify pairs of sources with profiles that are poorly or not comparable.

The SID assesses the similarity between factor/source profiles based upon a distance and acceptability thresholds expressed in relative uncertainty units. Such distances, which are proportional to the Canberra distance (Lance and Williams, 1966), are independent from the species concentration, and, therefore, are expected to be less influenced by very high values compared to Pearson. Unlike Pearson, SID is also sensitive to the amplitude (σ) of the variables. It follows that Pearson indicates how well the relationship between two variables can be described with a line no matter what the slope and intercept are, while SID tests only the linear model with slope 1 and intercept 0. This property makes SID more appropriate to be used for pairs of factor/sources profiles that are expected to be similar (i.e. belonging to the same source category). Another advantage of SID is that it can be calculated for theoretical profiles with only two species (e.g. ammonium sulphate) while the correlation for this specific but rather common type of profile with any other will always result in Pearson equal to 1.

The plots in Fig. 3 are useful to illustrate some of the properties of the indicators discussed in this section. The scatterplots represent the relative concentrations $x_{j,A}$ and $y_{j,B}$ of chemical species in two real wood burning source profiles A and B (Larsen et al., 2012). Fig. 3a shows the influence of organic carbon (OC) and elemental carbon (EC), whose concentrations are much higher than the majority of the species, on the Pearson. Pane b shows that logarithmic

transformation has little effect in reducing the high Pearson values driven by OC and EC. When the extreme values (OC and EC) are eliminated, the correlation between the two factor profiles falls below the acceptability threshold of 0.6 (Pane c). Similarly, the $ID_{j,ab}$ calculated using all relative concentrations and testing the compliance with a MAD equal to 60% of the concentration leads to values above unity ($SID = 1.1$) indicating little comparability between the profiles (Pane d).

This case based on measured source profiles shows how SID is less affected by scaling effects than Pearson in the evaluation of the similarity between two source profiles.

In order to define realistic SID acceptability thresholds for every source category, tests were conducted on a set of 169 source profiles from the database SPECIEUROPE (<http://source-apportionment.jrc.ec.europa.eu/Specieurope/index.aspx>) belonging to 31 different source categories. For few categories with a reduced number of profiles, those from SPECIATE were also used.

The relative MAD equivalent to $SID = 1$ was calculated for all the pairs of source profiles belonging to the same category and the 95th percentile was used to estimate the contribution of the source profile uncertainty (MAD_{sou}) to the $MAD_{rel,k}$ in each source category k (Table 3). The relative variability of the sources estimated with this method ranges between 0.52 and 1.07.

In Fig. 4 are shown the percentages of successful source/profiles observed in the two intercomparisons for the three indicators of similarity discussed in this section. The differences between SID and Pearson computed either with raw or log-transformed data reflect a) the more homogeneous representation of all the species in the profiles of SID and b) the more realistic limits of acceptability defined for every source category on the basis of the measured source profiles used for this indicator. The SID and the Pearson-log fall within a tolerance of 10% only in one third of the reported results. The percentage of reported results with successful SIDs is higher than those with successful P-log in the second round of the intercomparison and the opposite is observed in the first round of the intercomparison. This result confirms that the reported chemical profiles obtained using a real-world dataset as input are more heterogeneous than those obtained when using a synthetic dataset.

In addition, it was observed that the percentage of successful Pearson-log are too high in fully unconstrained tools like principal component analysis (PCA) and simple factor analysis (FA-MLRA)

Fig. 3. Scatterplots with the relative mass of different chemical species in two wood burning measured source profiles: a) raw data, b) log-transformed data using Equation 5, c) raw data excluding the two outliers (OC and EC), and d) raw data indicating distance to the identity line and the acceptability thresholds. OC: organic carbon; EC: elemental carbon.

Table 3

Relative maximum acceptability distance (MAD_{sou}) obtained as the 95° percentile of the MAD of all the pairs of source profiles in every source category in the database SPECIEUROPE.* SPECIEUROPE + SPECIATE,** SPECIATE.

	Source category	$MAD_{sou} = 0.95 P$	# profiles
1	Traffic	0.92	28
2	Gasoline exhaust	0.82	4
3	Road dust	0.93	15
4	Soil dust	0.96	20
5	Marine aerosol	0.52	3
6	Industrial	1.07	77
7	Iron and steel production	0.99	7
8	Foundries	1.03	6
9	Metal smelting	1.03	4
10	Cement	0.82	11
11	Ceramic	0.62	6
12	Power plant	0.84	10
13	Fertilizer production	1.00	9
14	Fuel oil burning	0.94	11
15	Coal burning	0.98	12
16	Coke burning	1.05	6
17	Natural gas burning	0.97	3
18	Boiler	0.98	8
19	Ship exhaust	0.67	14
20	Biomass burning	0.93	24
21	Wood burning	0.81	18
22	Pellet burning	0.93	3
23	Closed fireplace	0.91	16
24	Soft wood burning	0.76	3
25	Hard wood burning	0.59	4
26	De-icing salt	0.62	6
27	Cu smelter*	0.83	5
28	Steel production*	0.89	9
29	Lead smelter*	0.80	3
30	Gasoline exhaust**	0.98	8
31	Diesel exhaust**	0.87	9

due to the limitation of this indicator to deal with zero (and negative) values that are often reported by this poorly performing tools.

To decide whether a source/factor belongs to a given category the following criterion was used: if more than 50% of the preliminary tests fail, then the factor/source is considered dubious for the tested source category. In synthetic datasets, where “true” source profiles and contributions are available, only tests factor/source to reference source (fr tests) are taken into account. In real-world datasets, it is a good practice to remove the factor/sources that were declared dubious in the preliminary tests when calculating the reference value with the robust average algorithm (see Section 4.3).

4.2.2. Weighted difference test

The weighted difference (WD) is the relationship of the distance between two factors/sources (ID) and the measurements uncertainty of each species included in the factor/sources (Karagulian and Belis, 2012). It can be calculated from Equation (5) as follows:

$$WD_{ab} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{|x_{ja} - y_{jb}|}{\sqrt{u_{ja}^2 + u_{jb}^2}} \quad (8)$$

where u_{ja} and u_{jb} are the uncertainties of x_{ja} and y_{jb} , respectively. The WD domain ranges between 0 and $+\infty$. Setting the range of acceptability between 0 and 2.0 means that distances up to twice the combined uncertainty are considered acceptable.

If the Pearson or SID between two source/factors is acceptable, they likely belong to the same source category and the difference among them is expected to fall within their combined

Fig. 4. Comparison of the factor/source profiles that passed the preliminary tests using: Pearson, Pearson on log-transformed data (Pearson log) and standard identity distance (SID) in the two intercomparisons for receptor models. Between parentheses the intercomparison round and the number of tested factor/source profiles. Source categories codes: BioB, biomass burning; BRA, brakes; COPP, copper smelter; DIE, diesel exhaust; DUST, mineral dust; GAS, gasoline exhaust; INDU, industry; NO₃, nitrate; ROAD, road dust; SALT, road salt; SEC, secondary; SHIP, ship emissions; SO₄, sulphate; STEE, steel plant; TRA, traffic; ZINC, zinc smelter.

uncertainties.

In MFA the uncertainty of the output profiles is estimated using re-sampling and/or displacement methods while the CMB EPA 8.2 model performs a propagation of the input analytical uncertainty. A more detailed description of the methodology to estimate the uncertainty is given in the tool specific user guides (Watson et al., 1997; Norris et al., 2008, 2014) and discussed in methodological papers (Watson et al., 2008; Paatero et al., 2013; Belis et al., 2013).

By assessing WD together with Pearson or SID, it is possible to establish whether the uncertainties attributed to the factor/source profiles by participants are consistent with the observed differences. If a pair of factor/sources passes the Pearson or SID test, a WD > 2 indicates that the uncertainty has been underestimated in at least one of them. When one of the considered profiles is a reference source, the WD yields a straightforward indication of the goodness of the factor/source profile uncertainty estimation. The uncertainty of the chemical profiles tested against the reference derived from the synthetic dataset resulted in a 65% of accepted values (more details in Belis et al. (2015, submitted)).

4.3. Performance tests

The performance tests were developed on the basis of international standards for proficiency testing exercises (ISO 13528). The method consists of three milestones: a) the reference value (X), that is the expected value for reported SCEs, b) the target uncertainty (σ_p), that is the criterion to evaluate participants' performance, and c) the statistic to compare the values reported by participants with the reference (e.g. z-score).

As in the preliminary tests, the source categories are evaluated one by one. A reference value X for each source category is obtained either: a) by applying a robust analysis iterative algorithm (Analytical Methods Committee, 1989) to the SCEs of factor/source profiles belonging to the same source category (i.e. that passed the preliminary tests) or b) by formulation (see Section 3.2).

The (relative) standard deviation for proficiency assessment criterion (σ_p) was set, by analogy with the model quality objectives for PM₁₀ annual mean laid down in Directive 2008/50/EC, at 50% of the reference value.

The participants' scores can be calculated using different performance indicators. The z-score (Thompson and Wood, 1993) indicates whether the difference between a participant's estimated value and the reference value remains within the limits of the specified criteria

$$z_{(SCE)} = \frac{x_i - X}{\sigma_p} \quad (9)$$

where x_i is the SCE attributed to a given source category in every reported source apportionment i , X is the reference value and σ_p is the fitness-for-purpose criterion. The z-score interpretation is based on their allocation to one of the following three classes: the acceptance area (within the 95% confidence interval), the action area (the upper and lower extremes of the distribution representing 1% probability density) and the warning area (the areas between the acceptance and the action areas that totalizes a 4% of the probability density). The limits of these areas depend on the assumed distribution of the z-scores. In this study, we propose the following values: -1.96, -1.81, 3.87 and 3.99 obtained by fitting a kernel distribution (R package ks v. 1.9.2) to more than 200 unbiased z-scores after removing outliers and extracting the 0.005, 0.025, 0.975 and 0.995 percentiles to define areas with the same probability density as those used in the above mentioned methods for proficiency testing.

The z-scores provide information on the significance of SCE in source apportionment studies. Nevertheless, when the reference value is obtained by consensus from all or selected participants, common bias in the used methodologies with respect to the "true" value may be not detected.

The z'-score (ISO 13528, cited in Thompson et al., 2006) considers the uncertainty of the reference value (u_x) in addition to the target uncertainty (σ_p) to account for the reference value inaccuracy

$$z'_{(SCE)} = \frac{x_i - X}{\sqrt{\sigma_p^2 + u_x^2}} \quad (10)$$

The interpretation of z'-score is the same as the one of z-score. However, this approach has limited application when the reference

Fig. 5. Target diagram of the $RMSE_u$ (Thunis et al., 2012) obtained from the analysis of the SCE time series in Round1 (left pane) and Round 2 (right pane). The outer circle delimits the acceptance area and the inner circle represents the boundary of values with Pearson equal or higher than 0.7. The values for the factor/sources are indicated with crosses. Categories with most critical values are highlighted with different markers: squares, industry; circles, exhaust; diamonds, road salt.

value is obtained by robust analysis because in this case the x 's and X are correlated. In this study, z '-scores are only used to check the effect of the noise added to the input dataset on the evaluation of results.

Eighty-seven percent of the factor/source profiles reported in the two intercomparisons met the criteria for z -scores (more details in Belis et al. (2015, submitted)).

4.3.1. The uncertainty of the source contribution estimates

In source apportionment modelling, there are different sources of error: random error, modelling error, and rotational ambiguity (Paatero et al., 2013). One important source of random error is the one present in the input data due to the analytical uncertainty and variability. Modelling error may derive from wrong number of sources or variation of source profiles in time and is mostly contributing to the bias. Assessing rotational ambiguity is beyond the scope of this study. More details on this topic can be found in Paatero et al. (2002, 2013) and Paatero and Hopke (2009).

In this section, the zeta-score indicator is presented to assess the uncertainty of the SCEs reported by participants, which are commonly derived from the input data analytical uncertainty. The zeta-score (ζ) (ISO 13528, cited in Thompson et al., 2006) considers the uncertainties of both the participant and the reference values with no regard to the target uncertainty.

$$\zeta_{(SCE)} = \frac{x_i - X}{\sqrt{u_{xi}^2 + u_X^2}} \quad (11)$$

The critical values for the zeta-scores are obtained using the normal distribution. In order to assess participants' uncertainty estimation, zeta-scores should be used in conjunction with z -scores. Factor/sources with acceptable z -scores and poor zeta-scores likely have underestimated uncertainties. The zeta-score test indicated that the reported uncertainties in second round of the intercomparison were coherent with the one of the reference 68% of the time (Belis et al., 2015; submitted).

4.3.2. Assessment of the SCE time trends

In order to evaluate the uncertainty of the SCE time series (i.e. the time trend of the SCEs in every sample) an approach based on

the normalised RMSE, similar to the one described in Section 4.1.1, is adopted. The uncertainty normalised root mean square error ($RMSE_u$) depicts the bias and the random components of the modelled values scaled by twice the uncertainty of the observations (Thunis et al., 2012):

$$RMSE_u = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_1^n (m_n - r_n)^2}}{2u} \quad (12)$$

where, u denotes the uncertainty of the observations.

As shown in Equation (12), the modelled SCEs are scaled by the standard uncertainty of the reference SCE time series (u).

Similar to the $RMSD^*$, described in Section 4.1.1, the $RMSE_u$ indicates phase, amplitude and bias of the time trends. It is, therefore, considered a valid complement for the performance indicators used in proficiency tests that focus more on the bias and random uncertainty of the average SCE for the whole set of samples.

A convenient graphical representation of the indicators in Equation (12) is a target diagram in which the ordinate represents the bias (positive or negative) while the abscissa indicates if the standard deviation of the of a given time series of values is smaller (left) or larger (right) than $2u$ (Fig. 5).

The factor/sources ranking in the acceptance area are 74% and 90% in the first and second rounds, respectively. In these plots, the majority of the accepted values are placed in the left side of the target diagrams because the standard deviation in the reported factor/sources are lower than the established criterion ($2u$). The values of $RMSE_u > 1$ are mainly distributed in the first and third quadrants indicating that reported factor/sources with positive biases tend to have also a variance higher than the reference.

In these two rounds, scores in the rejection area are often associated with specific source categories: industrial and traffic in the first one and road salt in the second one. The scores in the industrial and traffic source categories are associated with the poor correlation of their time trends. The high road salt $RMSE_u$ values derive instead from the low SCEs and consequently high relative variance of the source/factors in this category (more details in Belis et al., 2015; submitted). Fully unconstrained models are those with the poorer performances while CMB 8.2, COPREM and EPA PMF v5 proved to be the most capable in reproducing the reference time trends. EPA PMF

v3 is the model with the widest range of scores, likely due to the highest number of results reported with this tool (#20).

5. Concluding remarks

The methodology proposed here provides a thorough evaluation of the output of a source apportionment study. Even though, it has been used on receptor models only, the proposed tests are suitable to assess any kind of source apportionment output (with source contribution estimates) in intercomparison exercises.

Our approach to develop a synthetic dataset by combining the output of a Chemical Transport Model with a real-world reference dataset made it possible to realistically reproduce source contribution patterns. Moreover, the combination of intercomparisons with real-world and synthetic datasets provides an optimal set-up to quantitatively evaluate both SCEs and the skills of the models and the practitioners to deal with the noise contained in the data.

One of the strengths of this methodology is that it relies on quantitative indicators that are widely used in proficiency tests and model quality assessment. This study demonstrates that existing indicators are suitable to test the source apportionment model output. In addition, the new indicator (Standardized Identity Distance) to compare source or factor profiles presented in this study provides added value compared to the existing indicators and may also find application in the identification of factors in source apportionment studies. Furthermore, the uncertainty normalised RMSE of the time series resulted a valuable complement of the performance indicators based on the SCE mean of the whole set of samples.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data related to this article can be found at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2015.08.002>.

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